

YEAR: 2024

CERTIFICATE OF PUBLICATION

AD EDUXIAN JOURNAL

A QUARTERLY MULTIDISCIPLINARY BLIND PEER REVIEWED
& REFEREED ONLINE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL

ISSN: 3048-7951

Google Scholar

This is to certify that the research paper entitled “Transforming Learning Opportunities and obstacles in 21st Century Education”, authored by “Dr. Kulwant Sin”, has been successfully published in ADEJ, Volume – 3, Issue – 2 (April-June 2026).

The paper has been assigned the DOI link: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19688536>

The manuscript is plagiarism-free and has undergone a rigorous double-blind peer review process, ensuring standards of originality, quality, and academic integrity as evaluated by the Review Committee of ADEJ.

Editor-in-Chief
AD EDUXIAN JOURNAL
(ISSN: 3048-7951)
Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, India

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